

Interface Engineering at Hole Transport Layer/Perovskite with Low band gap 2D-Carbon Nitrides For Solar Cells Fabrication

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Abstract: Interfacial engineering can effectively improve the device's performance by suppressing non-radiative recombination. The inherited ionic and hydrophilic nature of most of the semiconducting materials used for the hole transport layer in perovskite solar cells (PSCs) makes it susceptible to moisture. This is one of the factors that compromise the long-term durability of PSCs. In this contribution, we report the synthesis and characterization of polymeric carbon nitride-based 2D materials with composition C_3N_x (where $x = 3$ or 5) and their placement as an interfacial layer between hole selective and perovskite layer in the inverted PSCs. By so doing the interfacial engineering with 2D polymeric materials, suppress the redox reaction between Ni^{3+} in NiO_x and organic cation presence in perovskites to improve the stability. The interlayer suppressed the interfacial charge accumulation at the grain boundaries of perovskites and lower the non-radiative recombination, measuring a higher shunt resistance and amplified fill factor

1. Introduction

Solution-processed photovoltaics (PVs) employing halide perovskite as a light harvester are a potential bet for renewable energy generation due to their remarkable optoelectronic features, and cost competitiveness with crystalline silicon-based PVs.¹ However, the low device reproducibility and long-term stability, mostly induced by irradiation of light source, moisture corrosion, ionic migration, and oxygen infiltration under operational conditions obstruct its immediate commercial applicability.²⁻⁶ The further enhancement in PCE of PSCs has been restricted by charge recombination at different interfaces between the interlayers in perovskite thin films⁷ and their chemical stability. Accordingly, two representative device structures in which PSCs can be fabricated are planar and mesoscopic architectures.⁸ In particular the planar configuration has attracted considerable attention due to its low-temperature fabrication methodology and less hysteresis, the light-harvesting layer is sandwiched between the hole transport layer (HTL) & electron transport layer (ETL).^{9,10}

Similar to any device, the interface between perovskite and HTL remains vulnerable also in the PSCs in terms of losses because it traps the charge carriers at the interface within the perovskite and charge extraction layer. This also instigates the irreversible degradation mechanism caused by moisture.¹¹ Particularly, most organic HTLs such as Spiro-OMeTAD or PTAA in their pristine form show lower charge carrier mobility, and doping is required. In most cases, organic hygroscopic materials are used as a dopant to achieve competitive PV properties.¹² However,

the dopants accelerate the degradation process in the HTL and in the perovskite layer, which affects the stability of PSCs.¹³ Alternatively, a couple of inorganic materials such as VO_x ,^{14,15} WO_3 ,^{16,17} CuI ¹⁸, and NiO_x ^{19,20} have been used as HTL in PSCs. Particularly, NiO_x has been explored in the majority as compared to other inorganic materials due to its ease of preparation, suitable work function, and relatively higher optical transmission.^{21,22} However, a redox reaction between Ni^{3+} in NiO_x and organic cation in the A-site of perovskite compromises the chemical stability of perovskite.²³ Therefore in cases where NiO_x as HTL is being used in PSCs, it is imperative to develop new strategies to improve the interface through modification and engineering of HTL. Recently, 2D materials have emerged as effective remedies in many different photoconversion applications due to their distinctive properties such as high surface area, short diffusion path length for photoexcited charge carriers, and mechanical, electronic, and optoelectronic properties.²⁴ Particularly, metal-free carbon nitride-based polymeric 2D materials as passivation or as an additive in the PSCs have attracted considerable attention due to their chemical, mechanical and optoelectronic properties.²⁵⁻²⁷ Chen *et al.*, introduced $g-C_3N_4$ quantum dots as an active layer in the PSCs to enhance the conductivity and charge transfer carriers.²⁸ Followed by this a convenient strategy to improve the crystallization process by introducing the $g-C_3N_4$ in the perovskite layer was developed. The incorporation of $g-C_3N_4$ in the perovskite layers improves crystallinity, yields large grain size through the control of crystallization kinetics, and lowers intrinsic defects density by passivating the charge

recombination centers in the grain boundaries.²⁶ By blending *g*-C₃N₄ with perovskite precursors material without activating subdued light absorption improves charge transfer ability in the PSCs.²⁹

Polymeric carbon nitride-based 2D materials such as C₃N₃, C₃N₅, C₂N, etc. have a carbon-nitrogen ratio different from conventional *g*-C₃N₄ and possess intriguing optoelectronic properties.³⁰ The first principle calculations reported showed that the intrinsic electric field band alignments in C₃N₅ suppress the recombination of photoexcited charge carriers and improve the photocatalytic overall water-splitting efficiency.^{31,32} Blending of C₃N₅ with perovskite {MA_xFA_{1-x}Pb(I_{0.85}Br_{0.15})} measured a PCE up to 16.7 % and outperformed the *g*-C₃N₄ in their case.³³ The incorporation of 0.075 mg/ml of C₃N₃ into the precursor solution for the synthesis of perovskite resulted in improved stability as well as efficiency as compared to the control devices.³⁴ The exploitation of 2D carbon nitride-based materials in PSCs is of significant interest.

Here, we report the synthesis and characterization of polymeric C₃N₃ and C₃N₅-based 2D materials with tailored electro-optical and chemical properties. The structure and composition of the as-synthesized 2D polymers were established using an array of spectroscopic (FT-IR spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopy, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy [XPS], and microstructure (scanning electron microscopy [SEM] and transmission electron microscopy [TEM] and X-ray diffraction [XRD] techniques. These 2D polymeric materials are then introduced as an interfacial layer between the HTL and perovskite to align the energy levels and surface treatment of the perovskite. This allowed us to obtain an upgraded fill factor (*FF*), which can be attributed to the suppressed non-radiative recombination and enhanced photo-induced charge transfer dynamics at the perovskite/HTL interface. Assumably, the interlayer suppressed the interfacial charge accumulation at the grain boundaries of perovskites and lowered the non-radiative recombination. Notably, with the usage of an inorganic HTL, an upgraded *FF* was recorded. Arguably, owing to the inherent mechanical properties of these 2D polymer materials and avoiding the acid-base complex formation due to the presence of NiO_x atop perovskites will help to improve stability.

2. Experimental section

Materials

The chemicals for perovskite were purchased from either Dyesol or Tokyo Chemical Industry (TCI) and were used without further purification. [60]PCBM >99.5 % and Bathocuproine (BCP) were purchased from Solenne BV and TCI, respectively. Nickel (II) nitrate hexahydrate (Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, 99.999 %) and NaOH were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. Chlorobenzene (CB, 99 %), isopropanol (IPA, 99.9 %), ethanol (EtOH, 99 %), anhydrous dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, 99.8 %), and N, N-dimethylformamide (DMF, 99.8 %) were purchased from Acros Organics. Cu foil was purchased from Nimrod Copper Co. (>99.9%, thickness of 0.0254 cm) and Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, melamine, hydrazine, cyanuric chloride, and NaOH were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich.

Synthesis of C₃N₃ 2D materials:

Synthesis of C₃N₃: In a typical procedure,^{35,36} we used stainless steel lined reactor system for the synthesis of polymeric C₃N₃ 2D material (Figure S1) through solid-state chemistry. Briefly, 2 g of cyanuric chloride and a roll of fresh copper foil (0.05mm thick copper foil cleaned with acetone in an ultra-sonicator for 2 hours and dried using a stream of N₂ gas) were added to the steel reactor in an argon atmosphere. The sealed reactor was heated up to 250 °C for 20 hours under an argon atmosphere at a pressure of 20 megapascals. After the specified time the reactor was cooled down to room temperature. The copper foil with the deposited 2D polymeric film was removed and washed with deionized (DI) water. Afterward, the 2D polymeric films were scratched off from the copper foil using a spatula and again washed with ethanol and DI water in an ultra-sonicator using centrifugations for three to four cycles (Figure S2). Followed by centrifugations, the solid was collected and dried in a vacuum oven at 80 °C. (Yield ~ 75%).

Removal of copper impurities: The obtained dried samples were ground to powder in mortar and pestle and transferred to 100 ml centrifuge vials. Freshly, prepared 80 ml of 10 % HNO₃ aqueous solution was then added to a centrifuge vial and ultrasonicated for one hour, followed by centrifugation to remove the copper impurities. The above step was repeated three to four times and assured that there were bubbles generated and the aqueous solution turned to deep green-blueish color.

Later the sample was washed with 10 % HCl using an ultrasonic bath for 2 hours and then centrifuged (4000 rpm) with ethanol and DI water for three cycles. Followed by centrifugations, the obtained solid was dried in a vacuum oven at 80 °C. (Yield ~ 47%, shown in Figure S2).

Synthesis of C₃N₅ 2D materials

Synthesis of 2,5,8-triamino-s-heptazine (Melem): Melem was synthesized according to the reported procedures with slight modifications.³³ Briefly, in the first method (Figure S3), 5 g of melamine was heated in a tube furnace at 400 °C at 5 °C/minutes for 6 hours in an alumina crucible under inert conditions. For the second method, 5 g of melamine was first heated in a tube furnace at 330 °C at 5 °C/minute for 2 hours in an alumina crucible under the inert condition to obtain melam and then 4 g of melam was heated in a tube furnace at 400 °C at 5 °C/minute for 6 hours in alumina crucible under the inert condition to obtain melem. After cooling to room temperature, the obtained off-white yellowish color powder was suspended in DI water and refluxed for 2 hours for the removal of unreacted melamine and other impurities. The resulting off-white powder (2.5g) melem was collected after centrifugations and dried at 50 °C in the oven. It is worth mentioning, that both methods resulted in the successful synthesis of melem.

Synthesis of melem hydrazine or 2,5,8-trihydrazino-s-heptazine hydrazine (MH): melem hydrazine hydrate was synthesized by a slightly modified established procedure through a hydrothermal reaction of hydrazine hydrate with melem (Figure

S4). Briefly, 2 g of melem was dispersed in 20 ml of 80% aqueous solution of hydrazine hydrate and sealed in a 50 ml Teflon-lined autoclave. This Teflon-lined autoclave was introduced in the drying oven at 140 °C for 20 hours. After 20 hours, the autoclave was cooled to room temperature and subsequently, the prepared yellowish suspension was transferred to a 200 ml beaker and 10% of aqueous HCl solution was slowly added with stirring to control a pH of up to 2. The suspended white unreacted melem solid residue was removed through filtration. The filtrate was further precipitated with the addition of a 10% aqueous solution of NaOH by adjusting pH to around 8. This process was repeated for further three cycles. Finally, the obtained solid product 2,5,8-trihydrazino-s-heptazine (melem hydrazine hydrate) was washed three times with DI water, then with ethanol, and dried in an oven. The characteristics of analytical and spectroscopic analysis of the product matched with the reported literature.

Synthesis of C₃N₅ polymer: The obtained 2,5,8-trihydrazino-s-heptazine (melem hydrazine) was heated in a tube furnace at 450 °C at ramping of 2 °C/minutes and holding the temperature for 120 minutes under inert conditions. After cooling to room temperature, the final product bright orange color powder was obtained and further used for PSCs fabrication (Figure S5).

Fabrication of perovskite solar cells

NiO_x nanocrystals (NCs) synthesis: NiO_x NCs were prepared according to the reported procedures elsewhere, with modifications noted herein.³⁷ Briefly, 25 mmol Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O was dissolved in 50 mL of deionized (DI) water to obtain a dark green solution. The pH at 10 was maintained with a dropwise addition of NaOH (10 mol/L) while stirring for 30 min. The obtained colloidal precipitation was thoroughly washed with DI water five times via ultracentrifugation and dried at 90 °C overnight under a vacuum. The obtained green powder was calcined for 2 h at 275 °C to obtain a dark-black powder. 15 mg/ml NiO_x NCs ink was prepared by dispersing the as-synthesized NiO_x NCs in DI water. The above solution was ultrasonicated at 45 °C for 1 h and filtered using a 0.22 μm nylon filter.

HTL solution preparation: solution preparation of CN-based materials was carried out by ultra-sonication of 5 mg of materials in 1 ml of isopropanol/absolute ethanol (70/30, v/v) mixture for 8 h at 45 °C and rest for 30 min. The obtained solution was collected and subjected to ultracentrifugation for 30 min at 2000 rpm. 80% of the supernatant was carefully collected and precipitation was discarded. The final concentration was adjusted to 1 mg/ml by adding the mixture of isopropanol/absolute ethanol (70/30, v/v).

Device fabrication

The laser-etched FTO-coated glasses (TEC15) were thoroughly cleaned by sequential sonication with Hellmanex II (2 vol.%) solution, deionized water, ethanol, acetone, and isopropanol for 20 min each step. After being dried by compressed airflow, the substrates were further treated with UV-ozone for 30 min before use. NiO_x films were formed atop FTO substrates by spin coating at 4000 rpm for 35 s with 2000 rpm/s acceleration, followed by annealing at 150 °C for 30 min. The 1 mg/ml

solution of CN-based material was spin-coated on the NiO_x layer and annealed at 60 °C for 5 min to achieve the desired interfacial layer. The samples were transferred immediately (to avoid moisture absorption to the samples) to the argon-filled glovebox under controlled moisture and oxygen conditions (H₂O level: <1 ppm and O₂ level: <10 ppm) and annealed for another 5 min at 60 °C. The triple-cation-perovskite precursor solution was prepared according to the previous reports containing CsI (0.10M), FAI (1.05 M), PbI₂ (1.24 M), MABr (0.12 M), and PbBr₂ (0.12 M) in an anhydrous solvent mixture of *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF) and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) with 4:1 vol ratio.^{1,38} The perovskite precursor solution was then spin-coated in a two-step spin-coating program set at 1000 rpm and 6000 rpm for 10 and 30 s, respectively. During the second spin step, 112 μL of chlorobenzene was dripped 10 s prior to the ending of the program followed by annealing at 100 °C for 1 h. The PCBM solution of 15 mg/ml in chlorobenzene was spin-coated at room temperature on perovskite film at 1000 rpm (500 rpm/s) for 20 s and vacuum dried for 5 min. Then thin bathocuproine (BCP) was deposited atop of PCBM layer by spin-coating at 5000 rpm for 40 s followed by evaporating Ag (100 nm, <1 Å/s) in a thermal evaporator under low vacuum conditions (10⁻⁷ Torr). The control device was fabricated according to the above procure without the interfacial layer.

Device characterization: Current density–voltage (*J*–*V*) curves shown were performed using an Oriel solar simulator (Newport) producing 1 sun AM1.5G (100 mW cm²), 3A sunlight and were recorded by applying an external potential bias to the devices. The generated photocurrent was recorded at a scan rate of 100 mV/s (pre-sweep delay: 10s) with the help of a Keithley 2604 source meter and 0.09 cm² black metal mask as the active area. IPCE measurements were carried out using a 150 W xenon lamp attached to a Bentham PVE300 motorized 1/4m monochromator as the light source.

3. Results and Discussion

C₃N₅ was synthesized using two steps as earlier reported.³³ The first step involves the synthesis of 2,5,8-triamino-s-heptazine (melem) using melamine as a precursor using solid-state synthesis under inert conditions followed by its derivatization with hydrazine using hydrothermal. In the second step, the 2,5,8-triamino-s-heptazine hydrazine hydrate was converted to polymerized carbon nitride (C₃N₅) in the tube furnace under the inert condition at 450 °C. C₃N₃ was synthesized using the Ullman reaction employing cyanuric chloride as precursor and copper sheet as catalyst and support. The product was deposited onto a copper sheet (Figure S2) which was carefully scratched from the copper sheet. The coordinated copper inside the triazine rings was removed by repeated washing with 10% HNO₃ and 10% HCl and MilliQ water. The synthesis details for both 2D carbon nitride-based polymers are mentioned in the experimental section provided as supplementary information. The chemical structures and reaction schemes along with reaction conditions are provided in the supplementary information (Figure S2 - S5). The structure and crystalline nature of the as-synthesized low band gap 2D carbon nitrides C₃N₃ and C₃N₅ were investigated using an X-ray diffraction

pattern (XRD) which exhibited a distinctive broad reflection at 2θ value 27.2° and 27.6° respectively. These reflections correspond to the (002) plane which is related to the inter-layer reflection of graphite-like stacking in conjugated aromatic segments (C-N). However, the slight increase in the 2θ value for C_3N_5 as compared to $g-C_3N_4$ could be due to the presence of higher π electron density.³³ Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy spectra were employed to determine the functional groups present in C_3N_5 and C_3N_3 and display a series of distinct bands in the region from 1200 to 1700 cm^{-1} . These could be indexed to the C-N stretching of heptazine rings in the aromatic nucleus. A prominent peak centered around 775 cm^{-1} corresponds to the molecular vibrational modes of triazine rings. The broadband in the high-frequency region at around 3400 cm^{-1} could be indexed to symmetric and antisymmetric -NH₂ stretching modes. In the case of C_3N_5 , two new peaks emerged at 1073 and 1025 cm^{-1} corresponding to the N-N stretch of azo linkage and -NH₂ rocking vibration respectively.³³ The chemical structure, phase crystallinity, and molecular structure of the as-synthesized conjugated polymers were further characterized using Raman spectroscopy. The Raman spectra for the C_3N_5 displayed a sharper G band that could be due to the contribution of the C=N stretching mode. Additionally, two small peaks were observed centered at 1025 and 1160 cm^{-1} , which can be assigned to the mixed vibration of heptazine moiety and azo stretch. Whereas the Raman spectra of C_3N_3 showed a very condensed structure with two peaks centered at 1320 and 1596 cm^{-1} related to the D and G bands.³³ We noted that C_3N_5 shows good absorption in the visible region, while the C_3N_3 showed an extended absorption edge in the visible region with a prominent broad absorption band in the near-visible region around 400 nm . The energy bandgap calculated using DRS spectra showed 2.5 eV and 1.7 eV for C_3N_3 and C_3N_5 respectively.

Figure 1. (a) Chemical structure of tri-s-triazine-based C_3N_3 and azo linked low band gap C_3N_5 , (b) XRD pattern, (c) FTIR spectra, (d) Raman spectra, (e) DR-UV-Vis spectra, and (f) $[F(R)hu]^{1/2}$ vs. $h\nu$ plot for C_3N_3 and C_3N_5 .

The microstructures of the C_3N_3 and C_3N_5 were deduced (Figure S6) by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The SEM image of the C_3N_3 reveals its layered structure, which appears with wrinkled structures as marked by the arrow inside the SEM

image (Figure S6a). The C_3N_5 also indicated the 2D layered structure (Figure S6b). The 2D layered morphology was further established using high-resolution transmission microscopy (Figure 2). The typical TEM images of C_3N_5 are shown in Figures 2 a & b. The zoomed-in TEM image (Figure 2b) showed layers stacked onto each other as indicated by steps (marked by arrows). The TEM images for C_3N_3 (Figure 2 c & d) also revealed the 2D morphology. The HRTEM data for both C_3N_5 and C_3N_3 do not reflect any lattice fringes. However, it is worth mentioning that as-synthesized C_3N_3 (before washing with mineral acids to remove copper) showed clear lattice fringes (Figure S7).

Figure 2. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images, (a) TEM image of C_3N_5 showing the layered structure, (b) high-resolution TEM image indicating the layers stacked as marked by arrows, (c) TEM image showing the 2D structure of C_3N_3 and (d) high-resolution TEM image indicating the amorphous nature of C_3N_3 .

The chemical composition and chemical states of different elements in the as-synthesized samples C_3N_3 and C_3N_5 were determined using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) (Figure 3a-d.). The high-resolution C1s XPS spectrum of C_3N_3 (Figure 3a) shows three deconvoluted peak components, in which the peak at 284.8 eV originated from the sp^3 C-C group which bridge the two triazine rings while the deconvoluted peak observed at 284.6 eV attached to N in aromatic structure (N-C=N). The peaks observed at 289.4 eV were assigned to sp^2 aromatic C attached to C-N₃ or NH₂ group (C-NH₂).³² Similarly, C_3N_5 shows deconvoluted three peaks centered at 283.5 , 287.1 , and 289.1 eV , corresponding to the graphitic carbon, sp^2 aromatic carbon N-(C₃) and (N-C=N) or C-NH₂, respectively. The high-resolution XPS of N 1s of C_3N_3 shows two peaks after deconvolution where the predominant peak at ca. 398.12 eV is assigned to sp^2 N percent in triazine rings as C=N-C, while the medium peak at 399.3 eV corresponding to bridging N atoms in N-(C)₃.²⁷ The N 1s spectrum of C_3N_5 shows the three deconvolution peaks at 397.1 , 398.8 , and 400.5 eV , respectively. The two peaks with a binding energy of 397.1 eV and 398.8 eV were assigned to secondary and tertiary nitrogen present in the aromatic ring structure while 400.5 eV exhibited the presence of bridging C-N=N-C type nitrogen and some of the residual primary -NH₂ groups.

Figure 3. High-resolution XPS spectra of; (a) C 1s and (b) N 1s for C_3N_3 and (c) C 1s and (d) N 1s for C_3N_5 .

We probed the usage of low dimensional carbon nitrides to serve as an interfacial layer in inverted PSCs in a configuration of FTO/ NiO_x/C_3N_x ($x=3, 5$)/CsFAMA/PCBM/BCP/Ag, where CsFAMA denotes triple-cation-based perovskite $[Cs_{0.1}(FA_{0.9}MA_{0.1})_{0.9}Pb(I_{0.9}Br_{0.1})_3]$. The device architecture is illustrated (Figure 4a) and device fabrication steps are detailed in the experimental section. The control device without an interfacial layer measured a PCE of 16.69% with an open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) of 1001.89 mV, short-circuit current density (J_{sc}) of 22.79 $mAcm^{-2}$, and fill factor (FF) of 73.07%, (Figure 4b and Table 1). The performance of the C_3N_5 incorporated device increased to 17.17%, with a V_{oc} of 1003.48 mV, J_{sc} of 22.52 $mAcm^{-2}$, and noticeably enhanced FF of 75.95%. Upon the C_3N_5 interface layer, a relatively reduced series resistance (R_s) and higher shunt resistance (R_{sh}) were observed (Table S4). The high R_{sh} can be correlated to synergistically suppressed charge build-up and reduced recombination losses at the perovskite/ NiO_x interface, which allowed us to achieve high FF with C_3N_5 -based PSC.

Figure 4. (a) Schematic configuration of PSCs, (b) J - V curves of the PSCs employing different interfacial layers, and (c) the corresponding EQE and integrated current densities of the devices.

In contrast, the device with C_3N_3 showed a significantly lower PCE of 10.99%. We hypothesize that the poor interfacial compatibility of C_3N_3 at the NiO_x /CsFAMA interface, leading an undesirable photo-charge transfer at the interface as observed by higher R_s and lower R_{sh} , which results in reduced FF, J_{sc} , and V_{oc} . Adverse device properties also originated from lower solubility/ complete miscibility of C_3N_3 in the solvent, which

induces thickness variation of the interface layer. However, we assume that the solvent behaves similar way on the NiO_x film in each interlayer deposition since the same solvent-mixture and deposition parameters were used. We further, calculated the hysteresis factor following the equation; $HF = [PCE_{RS} - PCE_{FS}] / PCE_{RS}$, where PCE_{RS} and PCE_{FS} represent the PCE from reverse and forward scans, respectively (Figure S8 and Table S1). The HF for the control and C_3N_5 -based devices is 1.4 and 0.82%, respectively, which indicates that the C_3N_5 -based device exhibits a narrow hysteresis. The integrated current densities from the incident photon-to-current efficiency (IPCE) spectrum were 21.46, 16.52, and 21.23 $mAcm^{-2}$ for control, with C_3N_3 , and with C_3N_5 devices, respectively (Figure 4c), which are in agreement with J_{sc} values detected from J - V characteristics. Expectedly, the C_3N_3 shows lower performance which is corroborated by the PV properties.

Table 1. Photovoltaic parameters of the champion devices without and with interfacial layers.

Device	Scan direction	V_{oc} (mV)	J_{sc} ($mAcm^{-2}$)	FF (%)	PCE (%)
Control	RS	1001.89	22.79	73.07	16.69
	FS	1001.72	22.79	72.04	16.45
with C_3N_3	RS	890.16	17.21	71.74	10.99
	FS	893.74	16.98	69.66	10.57
with C_3N_5	RS	1003.48	22.52	75.95	17.17
	FS	1001.67	22.56	76.62	17.31

Conclusions

In conclusion, we have reported the synthesis and characterization of carbon nitride-based 2D materials. The C_3N_3 and C_3N_5 are characterized for spectroscopic and structural characterization to decipher their 2D structure. These metal-free 2D materials are used to engineer the interface between the hole transport and the perovskite layer for solar cell fabrication. The devices fabricated using low band gap 2D material (C_3N_5), resulted in improved fill factor. The high FF stems from the high shunt resistance owing to synergistically suppressed charge build-up and reduced recombination losses at the perovskite/ NiO_x interface.

Keywords: carbon nitrides, interface engineering, perovskite solar cells, Stability.

Conflicts of interest

There are no known conflicts to declare.

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